

THE IMPACT OF TRADE OPENNESS ON UZBEKISTAN ECONOMIC GROWTH: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of trade openness on economic growth of Uzbekistan. The specific objectives are to: analyse the degree of relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan, and to identify the key determinants of trade openness in Uzbekistan. Data for the study were sourced mainly from the Food and Agricultural Organization statistical database (FAOSTAT), and it covers a period of 33 years between 1990 and 2022. The analytical techniques that were used in this study include the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) and the multiple regression analysis. The study concludes that a positive relationship ($r = 0.24$) exists between the trade openness and economic growth (proxied by GDP) in Uzbekistan. It was also concluded that exchange rate (local currency units per USD) ($\beta = 0.039$, sig = 0.00) and agricultural production (gross per capita production) ($\beta = 9.904$, sig = 0.00) have a strong positive and significant effect on trade openness in Uzbekistan. The study recommends that government should consolidate effort to further reap the benefits that comes from all cross-border exchange that the country is involved in and that government and the private sector should invest more in this sector of the economy as it has a great potential to increase trade openness and consequently increase economic growth and prosperity of the country.

Keywords: Trade Openness, Economic Growth, Uzbekistan.

INTRODUCTION

The effect of trade openness on economic growth is undoubtedly a subject of great interest among economists and policy makers globally. Evidence from the literature has consistently shown that trade openness is a significant contributor to economic growth in

both developed and developing economies (Frankel and Romer, 1999; Silajdzic and Mehic, 2017; Ibitoye, et al, 2018; Marilyne, Chantal, and Mariana, 2019; and Jarju, 2023). In actual fact, many international organizations like the World Trade Organization (WTO) are encouraging countries to integrate and engage in cross boarder exchanges with other countries. Through this, many countries are now implementing strategies that align and integrate their domestic economies with the world economy through liberalization and open trade policy via various channels. The unequal natural resources and skills distribution, further encourages international trade across borders (Rasoanomenjanahary, et al., 2022).

Currently, a huge number of developing countries have integrated trade openness concept in their respective developmental goals. Hence, trade openness has now become a trend in the modern economy. Frankel and Romer (1999) reported that exogenous cross-country changes in international trade are strongly correlated to a country's per capita GDP. The relationship between economic growth and trade openness has been theoretically controvertible. It is generally believed that trade boosts the economy. However, recent developments have shown that trade openness does not directly have a growth-enhancing effect on a country's economy. Instead, the integration into global economy is facilitated by trade, which in turn enhance the inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI) (Rasoanomenjanahary, et al., 2022). Grossman and Helpman (1991) revealed that trade openness facilitates technological advancement and consequently, increase productivity. According to Bond et al., (2005), trade openness also helps the economy to increase production, leading to increasing returns to scale. Meanwhile, trade openness reduces the inefficiencies associated with the allocation of resources in the short run, and on the long run, it enhances the translates to technological advancement, according to Ohlan (2018).

Uzbekistan is the second largest economy in the Central Asia sub-region (next to Kazakhstan); with a GDP of \$90.0 billion in 2023 (World bank, 2023). However, limited empirical research has concentrated on the impact and contribution of trade openness to the country's economy. Examining the outcome of trade openness on economic growth of Uzbekistan, therefore, deserves more empirical research attention at this period in the world economy when there are questions on whether a high degree of trade openness is truly beneficial. This study therefore aims to establish empirical evidence that shows the nexus between trade openness and Uzbekistan economic

growth. More explicitly, this research aims to provide answers to the following research questions:

I. What is the degree of relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan?

II. What are the key factors that could potentially boost trade openness in Uzbekistan?

The main objective of this research is to determine whether trade openness correlates with economic growth of Uzbekistan.

The specific objectives are to:

I. Analyse the degree of relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan, and

II. identify the key determinants of trade openness in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Trade (both imports and exports) is a vital component of a country's economy. Trade exposes a country to immense opportunities and advantages by exposing firms and products in a country to international competition, therefore, economies are encouraged to focus on areas of comparative advantage. This helps ensure that scarce skills and resources are deployed where they are most productive. Also, trade increases, amongst other things, competition (hence boosting productivity and innovation), and enables firms to capitalise on economies of scale from having access to larger markets.

According to (Igudia, 2004), trade openness can be described as the increasing integration of economic activities of the human societies around the globe. It could also connote the process of denationalization of clusters of economic, political and social activities that allows the free flow of goods and services across national boundaries. Therefore, it involves the growing economic interdependence of countries in a region through the increasing volume and varieties of cross-border transactions; international capital flows; as well as rapid and widespread technological change. The trade Openness Index is, however, an economic metric calculated as the ratio of country's total trade (i.e. the sum of exports plus imports), to the country's gross domestic product (GDP), therefore, the higher the index, the larger the influence of trade on domestic activities and the stronger that country's economy (UNCTAD, 2012). According to Evans (2007), Trade openness is believed to stimulate economic growth due to its influence in

integrating world economies and generating better markets. The study further affirmed the positive relationship between openness to trade and economic growth. His view was that the greater the intensity of competition resulting from openness to trade, the better will be the level of economic performance of nations.

Ajayi (2001), noted that a more open economy based on a single but influential premise, economic integration, would improve economic performance; offer new opportunities via expanded market and the acquisition of new technologies and ideas. Also, Uwatt (2004) submitted that African nations must stand up to face the demands of trade openness through meaningful policies that would promote and engender increased trade and capital inflows. He argued that countries that were open had experienced significant economic growth, while countries that were closed, only managed to grow at a very slow rate.

Hoeffler, (2002) affirmed positive relationship between openness to trade and economic growth. This view is in line with economic orthodoxy which presupposes that the greater the intensity of competition resulting from openness to trade, the better will be the level of economic performance of nations. Adopting the Sachs and Warner (1995) binary measure of openness, Hoeffler (2002) confirmed that openness to trade had a significant and positive impact on growth of nations via increased investment. It has been established that a higher degree of openness ensures better flow of foreign investment from developed countries to their developing counterpart (Evans, 2007). It is equally evident that the latter have not fully aligned their economies to allow the investment to stimulate satisfactory growth (Igudia, 2004). This has been attributed to such factors as inability to formulate investment friendly policies, political and social unrest, reliance on primary products for exports, institutional and structural imbalances, and weak infrastructural base (Aluko, 2004).

Empirical studies of trade openness have adopted a variety of methods. Scholars differ in their opinions on the method that provide a good assessment of trade openness. Scholars such as Kavoussi (1984) and Fosu (1990a) based their studies on cross-country data. Others like Abdulai and Jaquet (2002) did a country-specific study. However, the success recorded in the performance of many Asian economies (Asian Tigers) has given credence to the belief that openness to trade is a vital tool for economic growth (Evans, 2007). This is also supported by a World Bank (1987) report that the average growth

rates of the countries that are strongly open to trade were far higher than others that are less open economies, which recorded a decline in growth between 1973 and 1985.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Area:

The study area for this study is Uzbekistan. According to **Administrative-territorial structure of the Republic of Uzbekistan**, the Republic of Uzbekistan is situated in Central Asia, and covers a land area of 448.9 thousand sq.km. The territory in the north and north-east of the Republic of Uzbekistan borders with Kazakhstan, in the east and south-east with Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in the west with Turkmenistan, in the south with Afghanistan. The total length of the country border is 6221 km. Uzbekistan is a double landlocked country with a GDP of \$90.0 billion and population of 36.2 million (world bank, 2023). Uzbekistan is the world's second-largest cotton exporter and the fifth largest producer. The country relies heavily on cotton production as the major source of export earnings. Other major export earners include gold, natural gas and oil.

Fig. 1: Map of Uzbekistan

Source: Maps.google.com

Source of data:

The data used for this study were largely secondary in nature. The data, which covered a period of 33 years between 1990 and 2022, were sourced mainly from the Food and Agricultural Organization statistical database (FAOSTAT).

Analytical Techniques:

The analytical techniques that were used in this study include the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) was used to show the relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan, while the key factors that determine trade openness in Uzbekistan were identified using the multiple regression analysis following the Ordinary Least Square Estimate (OLS).

Model Specification:

Overall Openness Index (OPI)

The most natural measure of a country’s integration in a regional trade is its degree of openness. Let X, M and Y be country’s total exports, total imports and GDP, respectively. The country’s openness index was specified as:

$$OPI = \frac{X+M}{Y} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The higher the value of OPI, the more open the country is to trade. OPI was estimated for Uzbekistan for a period of 33 years between year 1990 and 2022.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC)

Pearson product moment correlation was widely used to measure the degree of the relationship between linear related variables.

The formula for calculating PPMC is given as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2] [n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- r = Pearson correlation coefficient
- x = trade openness
- y = economic growth (proxied by GDP)
- n = total number of years

Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression has been defined as the amount of change in (the value of) one variable associated with a unit change in (the value of) another variable. In this study, the Multiple Regression Analysis, therefore, helps to identify the key factors that determine trade openness in Uzbekistan.

The model is specified as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where:

Y = the dependent variable (trade openness).

β_0 = Constant

X_i = the matrix of independent/explanatory variables,

β_i = the regression coefficients,

ε = the error term.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Relationship between Trade Openness and GDP Growth in Uzbekistan

Table 1 presents the relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan. The Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) coefficient of $r = 0.24$ shows that a positive relationship exists between the trade openness and economic growth (proxied by GDP) in Uzbekistan. This agrees with the a priori expectation that trade openness positively enhances economic growth. However, the strength of the relationship is weak and not very significant. This further confirms the controvertible nature of the believe that trade openness does not directly have a growth-enhancing effect on a country's economy. Instead, it is a part of chains of events that aggregates to enhance the inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI), which ultimately has a direct positive effect on a country's economic growth.

Table 1: The Relationship between Trade Openness and GDP Growth in Uzbekistan

Correlations			
		OPI	GDP growth
OPI	Pearson Correlation	1	.240
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.186
	N	33	32
GDP growth	Pearson Correlation	.240	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.186	
	N	32	32

Source: Author's computation, 2024.

The Key Determinants of Trade Openness in Uzbekistan.

Table 2a presents the factors that determine the overall trade openness in Uzbekistan. Four independent variables were included in the model following a detailed review of the literature to identify factors that directly influence trade openness. The independent variables include: total FDI inflows (million USD), total FDI outflows (million USD), agricultural production (gross per capita production) and exchange rate (local currency units per USD). It was revealed that exchange rate (local currency units per USD) ($\beta = 0.039$, sig = 0.00) and agricultural production (gross per capita production) ($\beta = 9.904$, sig = 0.00) are the independent variables that have a strong and significant effect on trade openness in Uzbekistan. This is an indication that exchange rate is a major determinant of trade openness in Uzbekistan in agreement with a priori expectation. Also, the gross per capital increase in agricultural production increases the degree of trade openness in Uzbekistan. Even though the coefficient of total FDI inflows (million USD) is not a significant determinant of overall trade openness in Uzbekistan, the effect is observed to be positive. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) value of 0.961 indicates that 96.1% of the variations in overall trade openness index in Uzbekistan is accounted for by the independent variables captured in the model; while the remaining 3.9% are accounted for by the stochastic error term (ε). The adjusted R-squared of 0.941 implied that 94.1% of the variation in trade openness in Uzbekistan are explained by those independent variables that significantly affects OPI.

Table 2a: The Key Determinants of Trade Openness in Uzbekistan.

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1191.284	140.762		8.463	.000
	Total FDI inflows (million USD)	.018	.017	.097	1.068	.317
	Total FDI outflows (million USD)	-4.004	3.445	-.085	-1.162	.279
	Agricultural production (Gross per capita production)	9.904	1.552	.547	6.380	.000
	Exchange rate (Local currency units per USD)	.039	.003	1.205	11.649	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OPI

Source: Author's computation, 2024.

Table 2b: The Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.980 ^a	.961	.941	30.358
a. Predictors: (Constant), Exchange rate (Local currency units per USD), Total FDI outflows (million USD), Agricultural production (Gross per capita production), Total FDI inflows (million USD)				

Source: Author's computation, 2024.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The effect of trade openness on economic growth is undoubtedly a subject of great interest among economists and policy makers globally. Uzbekistan, being the second largest economy in the Central Asia sub-region has limited empirical research conducted on the impact and contribution of trade openness to the country's economy. Therefore, examining the impact of trade openness on economic growth of Uzbekistan deserves a greater attention. It is based on this premise that this study aims to establish empirical evidence that shows the relationship between trade openness and Uzbekistan economic growth. The specific objectives are to: analyse the degree of relationship between trade openness and GDP growth in Uzbekistan, and identify the key determinants of trade openness in Uzbekistan. Data for the study were gathered exclusively from the secondary source. The data which covered a period of 33 years between 1990 and 2022, was sourced mainly from the Food and Agricultural Organization statistical database (FAOSTAT). The analytical techniques that were used in this study include the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) and the multiple regression analysis.

The study concludes that a positive relationship exists between the trade openness and economic growth (proxied by GDP) in Uzbekistan, in agreement with a priori expectation that trade openness positively enhances economic growth. However, the strength of the relationship is weak and not very significant. This indicates that trade openness may not directly have a growth-enhancing effect on a country's economy. It was further concluded that exchange rate and agricultural production have a strong positive and significant effect on trade openness in Uzbekistan in agreement with a priori expectation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

I. Government should consolidate effort to further reap the benefits that comes from all cross-border exchange that the country is involved in. This will ensure that the weak relationship that currently exist between trade openness and economic growth in the country is strengthened.

II. Since increase in gross per capita agricultural production was revealed to be a major determinant of trade openness, both the government and the private sector should invest more in this sector of the economy as it has a great potential to increase trade openness and consequently increase economic growth and prosperity of the country.

III. Finally, the foreign exchange policies should be managed in such a way that it will continue to enhance international trade and further increase trade openness in Uzbekistan.

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